

Young people's views and experiences of youth vaping in their community

**A co-created study between embedded researchers and local
authority public health practitioners**

Lorna Dowrick

Victoria Shackleton

Saima Nazir-Desforges

Richard Gettings

Eleanor holding

Marie Rogerson

Catherine Homer

Carys Williams

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CRedit Author contribution statement

Lorna Dowrick (Sheffield Hallam University): Principle Investigator, Conceptualisation, methodology, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing-original draft, supervision, project administration. **Victoria Shackleton (City of Doncaster Council):** Conceptualisation, methodology, formal analysis, investigation, writing- review & editing. **Saima Nazir-Desforges (City of Doncaster Council):** Conceptualisation, methodology, formal analysis, investigation, writing-review & editing. **Richard Gettings (Sheffield Hallam University):** Conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, writing-review & editing. **Eleanor Holding (University of Sheffield):** conceptualisation, methodology, writing-review & editing. **Marie Rogerson (City of Doncaster Council):** Investigation, formal analysis, writing-review & editing. **Catherine Homer (Sheffield Hallam University):** Supervision, methodology, **Carys Williams (City of Doncaster Council):** Conceptualisation, methodology, writing-review & editing.

Contents

Acknowledgements	2
Funding statement	2
CRedit Author contribution statement	2
Contents.....	4
Executive Summary	7
Background	9
Young people and the use of vapes.....	9
Tobacco smoking and vape use.....	11
Motivators for use of vapes	12
Access to vapes.....	12
Rationale: why is research on YP and vaping in Doncaster needed?	13
Methodology.....	15
Co-creation process	15
Aims of the research:.....	15
Research objectives:	15
Research questions:.....	16
Public Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) and development of data collection tools.	16
Participant recruitment.....	17
Ethics and safeguarding	18
Data collection.....	19
Data analysis.....	19
Results.....	20
How do young people from across Doncaster perceive access to and use of vapes by their peers?	20
What do young people know about vapes and their impact?	24

What strategies do young people think would be most effective in supporting young people to understand the impact of the use of vapes?	28
Strengths and limitations	29
Key insights and recommendations	30
Reflections on the co-creation process	33
Reflections on the start of the study	34
Reflections on conducting the study	34
Reflections on the end of the study	36
Impact	37
Dissemination	37
Next steps	38
Conclusion	38
References	40

Executive Summary

Doncaster faces significant challenges in connecting people, places and businesses to economic and social opportunities. Life expectancy in Doncaster is below average for both males and females in England (OHID 2025).

In 2023, the City of Doncaster Council (CDC) was awarded funding by the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) for the Health Determinants Research Collaboration. The HDRC seeks to grow the Council's capacity to develop and use knowledge within decision-making processes leading to better outcomes for Doncaster citizens. The HDRC includes the provision of embedded researchers within CDC from two academic partner institutions- Sheffield Hallam University and the University of Sheffield.

In recent years the use of electronic cigarettes (vapes) has increased significantly by young people nationally (NHS 2022, ONS 2023). Locally, CDC surveys with young people (CDC 2022, 2023) have identified that specific groups of young people in Doncaster have been using vapes to a greater extent than others. These groups mirror existing health inequalities and disadvantage. The local school survey data (CDC 2022, 2023) also suggests that within Doncaster, regular use of vapes is more prevalent than occasional use. Vapes are less harmful than cigarettes but still have harmful effects on health. Young people's developing lungs and brains are more sensitive to the effects of vaping and the long-term impact remains unknown (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities 2022).

This study investigated the use of and access to vapes by young people in Doncaster. Qualitative fieldwork was undertaken with youth groups of young people aged over 13 years in four community settings in Doncaster. The study was co-created through a collaborative team of embedded researchers and local authority public health practitioners who were all involved in each stage of the study from conceptualisation to dissemination.

The results highlight the appeal of vaping products to young people and add important knowledge about the experiences of young people where vaping has been identified as more prevalent locally and which mirrors health inequality data. There was a lack of awareness amongst young people of the legal frameworks and health harms of vaping products. Young people made a range of suggestions for support to reduce vaping including providing accurate and clear information on vape harms, enhancing support services, and reducing vape access and appeal.

Learning from the co-created study points to a range of benefits of collaborative research undertaken in a local authority setting including increasing research capacity and knowledge sharing in a multi-disciplinary team. The study findings have also been disseminated through a publication in *Perspectives in Public Health* (Dowrick et al. 2025).

Background

Doncaster is the largest metropolitan borough by area in England with a dispersed population. It also has an industrial past and high levels of deprivation. Life expectancy in Doncaster is below average for both males and females in England (OHID 2025). These present significant challenges in connecting people, places and businesses to economic and social opportunities.

The City of Doncaster Council (CDC) has been funded by the National Institute for Health and care Research (NIHR) to deliver the Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC). The HDRC is a collaborative project between CDC, the University of Sheffield and Sheffield Hallam University and represents a significant investment to focus on further growing CDC's capacity to develop and use knowledge within decision-making processes leading to better outcomes for Doncaster citizens.

HDRC objectives are two-fold and interconnected:

1. To ensure enhanced use of research evidence to inform decision-making aimed at improving health and tackling inequalities across all functions and departments.
2. To build capability, capacity and motivation to undertake research and development to address the wider determinants of health across our HDRC.

This research is aligned to both HDRC objectives to ensure enhanced use of research evidence to inform decision-making aimed at improving health and tackling inequalities and to build research capacity.

Young people and the use of vapes

The use of vapes is increasing and at a greater rate than tobacco smoking. NHS data from the 'Smoking, Drinking and Drug use among young people in England' report (NHS 2022)

identifies that current vape use has increased to 9% in 2021, up from 6% in 2018. A study by Moore et al. (2020) also showed susceptibility to vaping (20%) was higher than smoking (12%) and Williams et al. (2022) found that regular vape use was more common than regular tobacco smoking (4.0% vs 2.9%). Moore et al. (2015) identified that primary school children were more likely to have used vapes (5.8%) than tobacco (1.6%) and ever use of vapes remained more prevalent than ever use of tobacco until age 14-15.

Research suggests that rates of experimentation with vapes are higher than more common use. Moore et al. (2015) concluded that many young people (including never smokers) have tried vapes, but that regular use is less common and is associated with tobacco cigarette use. This was also reflected in research by Bauld et al. (2017). They found in a review of five surveys conducted with young people in the UK between 2015–2017 that most vape experimentation does not turn into regular use, and levels of regular use in young people who have never smoked (tobacco) remain very low. More recently, Pinho-Gomes et al. (2023) conducted a survey with participants aged between 15 and 30 years and identified that about one in five participants currently used vapes at least monthly, with 1 in 10 using them daily. Amongst those using vapes at least monthly, 90% had used vapes containing nicotine.

Vape use is increasing, but importantly several studies have identified that many young people in the UK have inaccurate harm perceptions of vapes and nicotine (East et al. 2018, Hilton et al. 2016, Fulton et al. 2017) indicating that more awareness raising and education is important.

“Adolescents were aware that ECs were less harmful than tobacco, but many were unaware that they contain nicotine and the subsequent risk of addiction could lead to later tobacco use.” (Fulton et al. 2017).

The use of disposable vapes in the UK grew rapidly between 2021 and 2022 and this was especially the case for younger adults (Tatton-Birch et al. 2022). Tatton-Birch et al. also concluded that most young adult vapers in Great Britain now use disposable products (Tatton-Birch et al. 2022). The Action on Smoking and Health (ASH) survey of smoking and electronic cigarette (vaping) attitudes and behaviour among 11–18-year-olds, has been carried out annually by YouGov. Findings in 2023 stated that 69% said the most frequently used device

was a disposable (single use) vape up from 52% in 2022 and 7.7% in 2021 (Action on smoking and health 2023).

Recent NHS data highlighted that the prevalence of both regular and current users has increased for girls since 2018. Girls were now more likely than boys to be current vape users; 10% for girls compared to 7% for boys. Regular use was now similar (4% for boys and 5% for girls). Current vape use for 15-year-old girls increased from 10% in 2018 to 21% in 2021 (NHS 2022).

ONS data from 2023 also supports findings about increased vape use by young women. 6.7% of women aged 16-24 used vapes daily in 2022 compared to 1.9% in 2021 – with young women overtaking young men for vape usage (ONS 2023). The proportion of young women who used vapes occasionally also rose, from 7.1% in 2021 to 12.2% in 2022. This is compared to a total of 3.6% of 16- to 24-year-old men who use vapes every day, and 8.7% who use them occasionally.

In addition, Emerson (2023) conducted research on the prevalence of smoking and vapes among adolescents with/without intellectual disability in the UK and highlighted the use of vapes by young women with a potential intellectual disability as higher than among their female peers.

Tobacco smoking and vape use

There has been significant debate about the links between vapes and tobacco smoking and whether vapes offer a 'gateway' to tobacco smoking. Studies suggest that the relationship is more complex than linear pathways between vape and cigarette use (Measham et al. 2016, Delacy 2016, Lucherini et al. 2019, Brown et al. 2020, Hughes et al. 2021). Recent NIHR funded research also found that there is no sign that vapes promote smoking, but findings remain tentative, pending further research (Pesola et al. 2023).

Moore et al. (2020) identified that having a parent who vaped was associated with exposure to and positive perceptions of vapes but not smoking. Most children perceived vapes as used by adults to stop smoking (64%). Susceptibility to smoking and vapes were lower

among children who perceived vapes as cessation aids. They concluded that communicating to children the role of vapes as cessation devices for smokers may help to limit their appeal to young people.

Findings from research using data from an online survey with 11–18-year-olds found that vape use was more common among those who also smoked tobacco, with 9.0% of never vape users ever smoking tobacco, compared with 89.4% of regular vape users. Both smoking and vape use were associated with increasing age and use by others within the home, but not with social class (Williams et al. 2022). Moore et al (2015) reported no differences according to gender, ethnicity or family affluence for secondary school students ever using vapes.

Motivators for use of vapes

The role of flavours as a motivator for vape uptake was noted by a variety of studies (Measham et al. 2016; Hilton et al. 2016 and Notley et al. 2021). Measham et al. (2016) found that young people used vapes primarily for flavour combinations and to perform “tricks” and smoking cessation and nicotine consumption were less important motivations. This is also supported by research by Hilton et al. (2016). A systematic literature review conducted by Notley et al. (2021) also identified that the quality of the evidence on use of vape flavours by young people is low overall.

NHS research found that pupils who met people outside of home/school more frequently in the last four weeks were far more likely to be current vape users. 23% of pupils who said they met people every day were classified as current vape users, compared to only 1% for those who never met people outside of home/school (NHS 2022).

Access to vapes

According to the NHS survey data (2022) 1% of pupils who were regular vape users said other people gave them vapes, the most common of whom were friends (45%). Buying from any kind of shop increased from 29% in 2018, to 57% in 2021, with newsagent the most common type of shop (41%). Pinho-Gomes et al (2023) identified that vapes were mainly obtained from vape shops and used at home and the ASH survey found that the most frequent source of vapes (vapes) was shops (48%), closely followed by given (46%) and

informal purchase (26%). Fewer than one in ten (7.6%) gave the internet as a source (Action on smoking and health 2023).

Research on the use of vapes within the home highlighted that vape use was easily achievable for young people within the home and did provide a new opportunity for nicotine use in domestic spaces (Kirkcaldy et al. 2019). In some cases, young people's vape use in the home was accepted or tolerated by parents because it was perceived as less harmful than tobacco smoking and adult understandings of vape use were reportedly variable. There was also evidence of inconsistent methods of storing vapes within the home, which posed safety risks to younger children and easy access to vapes for others (Kirkcaldy et al. 2019).

Rationale: why is research on YP and vaping in Doncaster needed?

Since 2015, CDC has annually commissioned a pupil lifestyle survey to provide an overview of school pupil's perspectives on a variety of health and well-being issues. The survey in 2022 collected responses from 1505 secondary school age pupils and asked whether they had ever used any vapes. The findings suggested that of those who responded, 21% of year 10 pupils had tried vapes and a further 11% used them regularly. 8% of year 7 pupils had also tried vapes, rising to 12% in year 8 and 18% in year 9 showing an increase in use by school year. NHS data suggests that vape use amongst young people aged 14 years was 27% and for 15 years 39% in 2021 (NHS 2022) which may suggest lower rates of ever use within Doncaster. Data on ever use of vapes by region from the survey of smoking, drinking and drug use among young people in England (NHS 2022b) shows that Yorkshire and the Humber has the highest percentage for regions of ever use of vapes.

In Doncaster, since 2022, regular use was found to be more common than occasional use (7% compared to 6% for Y8 and Y10 pupils in 2022 and 7% regular use and 5% occasional use in 2023). While it is unclear how regular and occasional use are defined in different studies, this may suggest a difference from the literature which identifies use on a less frequent basis as more common than regular use (Moore et al. 2015, Bauld et al. 2017) although the studies were conducted in 2015 and 2017 and may therefore not reflect current trends. In 2021, CDC Pupil Lifestyle Survey data showed boys were more likely to use vapes regularly (2%) compared to girls at (1%). In 2023, the survey data showed girls were more likely to have ever

used vapes (16% of girls compared to 15% of boys). There was also substantial variation in regular use with 8% of girls stating that they use them regularly compared to 4% of boys.

The local survey for 2021 indicated that pupils on free school meals (FSM) were more likely to have tried vapes (31%). In 2022, for secondary school age pupils, young carers (46%) followed by FSM pupils (42%) and those with English as a second language (37%) were the groups most likely to have tried or be users of vapes. In 2023, FSM, SEN and ethnic minority pupils remained more likely to have tried vapes than any other group.

CDC were interested in exploring more detailed information about the nature of vape use in Doncaster by young people particularly in light of the increased prevalence of *disposable* vapes (Tatton-Birch et al. 2022, Action for smoking and health 2023).

Studies in the UK have been predominantly quantitative, and survey based, several qualitative studies were identified which primarily used group interviews/focus groups (Brown et al. 2020, Hilton et al. 2016, Kirkcaldy et al. 2019, Lucherini et al. 2017, 2018, Measham et al. 2016). Only one was longitudinal with interviews at two phases in the research (Hughes et al. 2021).

This study aimed to generate greater understanding of the use of vapes by young people in Doncaster to assist with the development of strategies to both prevent use by young people and to support cessation. A qualitative methodology was selected to explore in more detail views and experiences of young people in Doncaster building upon the general survey data previously generated.

Methodology

Co-creation process

As part of the broader HDRC project, this study also aimed to:

- Develop increased understanding of research and research processes amongst LA practitioners to support the development of a culture of evidence based practice and decision making
- Build research capacity within LA
- Share practice-based knowledge with embedded researchers
- Ensure study aligned to LA needs

LA practitioners and embedded researchers worked collaboratively throughout the research process from the development of the aims of the project through to the production of the report to co-create this study (O'Donnell et al. 2025). Reflections on the co-creation process are included at the end of the report (p30).

Aims of the research:

- I. Develop greater understanding of vape usage by young people in Doncaster.
- II. Explore strategies for preventing and supporting the cessation of use by young people who have never smoked cigarettes.

Research objectives:

- I. Conduct focus groups with diverse groups of young people from different population characteristics and places across Doncaster.
- II. Analyse the data using thematic coding to identify commonalities and differences between young people and their perceptions and understanding of vapes.
- III. Establish a set of recommendations for Doncaster public health and other stakeholders to inform their work with different groups of young people and vapes.
- IV. Produce a range of accessible materials reporting the findings of the project.

Research questions:

- I. How do young people from across Doncaster perceive access to and use of vapes by their peers?
- II. What do young people know about vapes and their impact?
- III. What strategies do young people think would be most effective in supporting young people to understand the impact of the use of vapes?

Public Patient Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) and development of data collection tools

Previous research has shown that prompts for discussion and aids such as statement cards with popular quotes (Lucherini et al. 2017) and newspaper headlines or website screenshots (Hughes et al. 2021) have been beneficial in research exploring vape use. Measham et al. (2016) utilised visual methods for recording discussion such as flipcharts and sticky notes to make the research process more interactive. The team were interested in the value of using more participative methods to engage participants in discussion and developed data collection tools in collaboration with the SHU Public Involvement in Research Group (PIRG) at the Advanced Well-being Research Centre (AWRC) and two small groups of local young people supported by their group youth workers. A range of creative tools were developed to aid discussion, including a pictorial chart, vignettes in the form of text message conversations and opportunities for producing posters or social media messages see examples in figures one and two below.

**Figure one: Poster template for activity one.
activity two**

Figure two: Example vignette for

Participant recruitment

Participants were recruited through existing youth groups supported by youth workers. Public health practitioner contacts were used to identify organisations or groups working with young people in Doncaster. The team worked with the community organisations to:

- I. Understand the setting protocols and procedures, agree roles and shared understanding of the project aims/parameters and consent procedures.
- II. Agree safeguarding and methods of support for young people.
- III. Review the methods and seek further guidance on adapting them to be as appropriate and engaging as possible for participants.
- IV. Recruit young people and obtain consent for the research.

The groups were chosen purposively to reflect where vaping has been found locally to be more prevalent based on data generated through the annual City of Doncaster Council Pupil Lifestyle Survey. Gift vouchers of £10 per person were offered to thank young people for their participation in the research.

Ethics and safeguarding

The study received ethical approval from Sheffield Hallam University Ethics Committee reference ER58604236. Participant information sheets and consent forms were provided to all potential participants. We also produced a short video format participant information sheet as an alternative guide to the research. Information sheets and consent forms were also provided in other languages for some of the participants' families where English was a second language.

Consent forms for participants were completed prior to the commencement of the first focus group. For participants under 16 years, a completed form signed by their parent/guardian was needed to be returned to the project team. We also provided an assent form for the young people aged under 16 to support their understanding and agreement to participate. For those over 16 years, a consent form was completed by the young person before the start of the research. The young people who expressed an interest in participating, and whose parents/caregivers consented to them participating, were invited to attend the focus groups by the youth workers.

It was made clear to the young people that expressing an interest in participation did not mean they were committed to participating, and that they did not have to take part if they did not want to. The participants were encouraged to participate in three focus groups, but it was highlighted that they could stop taking part at any point. Young people who were interested in participating, but who were unable to attend all three sessions were not excluded from participation. We also emphasised to the participants that the focus of the research is on their general views about the topic, and that they did not have to talk about personal experiences/stories if they did not want to. We agreed with each setting what the arrangements were for young people who did not wish to participate or did not have the required consent from parent/carers.

We informed participants that we would keep confidential the information they share with us with the exception of any concerns about their safety. We also agreed in advance who will be available from the partnering setting to provide support in the event of any safeguarding

issues or concerns. The focus groups were attended by at least two members of the research team alongside a member of staff from the setting.

Data collection

The study used participatory qualitative fieldwork with young people in small focus groups using the activities developed through PPIE sessions. Task one included a poster where participants were invited to respond to the prompt questions and add their thoughts in the form of sticky notes and/or via discussion. For task two, vignettes were produced in the form of text message prompts to aid discussion. For task three, participants were invited to discuss/write or design their own social media post or poster with a key message about vaping.

Sessions were audio recorded. Focus groups were conducted in community venues to encourage open feedback through a familiar, informal setting amongst peers. Young people were not asked directly about their own use of vapes as this was not necessary for the aims of the study and could create a barrier to participation if a young person felt they may be identified as someone who vapes.

There were three visits per setting:

- I. An introduction to the team and the research
- II. The focus group
- III. Sense-checking and feedback

The data collection took place between May and August 2024.

Data analysis

Data analysis was informed by a reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) methodology (Braun and Clarke 2006, 2019). Study team members without prior knowledge of the methodology were provided with bespoke training to aid participation in the analysis stage including an introduction to qualitative research and RTA. Analysis was then undertaken collaboratively.

This process was informed by a suggested methodology developed by Saunders et al., adapted to the needs of the project (Saunders et al. 2023). Data familiarisation and initial coding were undertaken by the lead researcher and at least two other members of the study team per transcript on an individual basis. This was followed by a facilitated group discussion of codes leading to the emergence of key themes within the data. The themes were subsequently organised according to the research questions established at the start of the study. Themes were written up and shared across the team to check for any further reflections.

Results

Basic anonymous demographic information was collected from participants at the start of the focus groups. 8 participants were male, 8 were female and one preferred not to say. 8 participants were from Gypsy or Irish Traveller, Roma or Other white backgrounds, 6 participants were from White British backgrounds, 3 were from Asian, Asian British or Asian Welsh backgrounds. YP were aged between 13 and 23 years old. Findings are presented below in relation to each of the research questions.

How do young people from across Doncaster perceive access to and use of vapes by their peers?

Activity one was designed to explore how young people from across Doncaster perceive access to and use of vapes by their peers. Using the poster to generate discussion, participants suggested that secondary school aged teens and pre-teens were most likely to use vapes.

“They usually start from Year 7” (Group Y).

However, they also reported some vaping among primary school children, though this was considered uncommon. Participants generally observed vaping across all genders, although a few suggested that girls were more likely to vape.

“I think you see more teenage girls with vapes in their hands than boys” (Group X).

Some participants commented on whether they believed young vapers were or had been cigarette smokers, with the main view that young people who vaped had no prior history of smoking cigarettes.

“I think particularly people who never used to smoke as well” (Group X).

These responses suggest that vapes are being used by young people who have not smoked cigarettes and is therefore not linked to supporting with smoking cessation.

When exploring how and when vapes are used by young people, the participants identified a range of behaviours indicating regular as well as occasional use. They also suggest that young people vape visibly in public spaces as well as more covertly. They commented on noticeable vaping before and after school hours and on weekends in public areas such as travelling to school, parks, and community spaces. Such high visibility of vaping supported the young people’s views that vaping was ‘everywhere’.

“Because now people think they can vape wherever and whenever they like, sat in buildings, sat in restaurants, on the bus, anywhere and everywhere” (Group X).

However, participants also noted secretive vaping behaviour, with young people using vapes discreetly in school bathrooms, their bedrooms, and away from family members.

“During breaks, usually like she said in the toilets” (Group Z).

“People do it more out of school, because in school you can get caught by teachers and they will tell your mum but outside of school no one knows, just strangers, that’s what you do, have secret places” (Group W).

These responses suggest that young people choose when to make their vaping visible or hidden, being more open in public spaces while concealing it from authority figures like school staff and family. Whether to vape visibly or in private may be influenced by the real or expected consequences of the behaviour.

“When I was at [name of event] they were actually doing it around the teachers...Teachers weren’t even bothered, they can’t stop them because it’s [name of event]” (Group Y).

We explored the reasons for using vapes and a notable theme related to vaping being seen as a desirable, adult activity.

“I think they do it because they think it’s cool” (Group X).

“I feel like kids now are in a race to grow up fast and...I want to do all these adult things now and it’s getting younger and younger” (Group X).

A few participants suggested that some young people vaped to help them manage their mood, in particular when feeling stressed.

“I have actually got a friend that does it to help with stress” (Group Y).

Vapes were described as having various appealing features in their design, flavours and promotion and this was described as an important factor for young people.

“It’s ones that’s shine up, all like different flavours and stuff like that” (Group X).

Some of the young people described brand names of vapes, whilst others talked about the products more generally. A preference for disposable vapes which tend to have more design features was noted alongside their convenience.

“Because they are easy, you don’t have to sit and wait for your liquids online, or you don’t have to go to the shop to get your liquids and coils... a disposable one you just take it out of the packet and smoke it, easy, easily accessible” (Group X).

The discussion also considered the role of peers for young people who vape. The participants highlighted that whilst peers do play a part, this was in the context of wanting to align their behaviour to others and wider social norms, as opposed to peers ‘pressuring’ young people into vaping.

“Probably like them just doing it together...” (Group Z).

YP1: “... it’s cool to vape.

YP2: I wouldn’t say peer pressure.

YP1: But if you don’t vape, you’re not cool sort of thing” (Group X).

This effect was noted within in-person interactions in school or the community as well as being experienced online, with exposure to social media content from older young people. On social media, vaping content appears in different forms, it can be dedicated posts showcasing vaping tricks or displaying vaping devices.

“People keep them (empty vapes) like to show off how many vapes they have had”

“They put videos of them blowing rings and stuff as well

And they put videos on...whatever social media they have got really” (Group X).

Vaping may not be the main focus, particularly in social media content from older individuals documenting their social activities. In these cases, vaping devices appear as incidental elements within broader lifestyle content.

“You see photos of people on nights out, you know vapes in their hand, everyone has got a vape in their hand” (Group X).

This exposure both online and offline, may contribute to a normalisation of vaping behaviour amongst young people. The role of family members was also discussed with some instances of family members providing access to vapes, but conversely for other young people family were the reason for not vaping or vaping in secret.

“Some ask their parents to like buy them vapes, not all” (Group Z).

Wider discussions regarding access to vapes suggested they were easily accessible and primarily purchased or accessed in person. Local shops were identified as the most common location for obtaining vapes, this could be the young person purchasing themselves as the vendor was selling illegally to young people and may be aware of this.

“Some shops need ID but others just allow you to buy vapes” (Group W).

Other methods for access for young people included having older friends or siblings purchase them on their behalf, as well as parents purchasing them.

“Older brothers or sisters to go buy their vapes” (Group W).

Apart from shops, other methods for obtaining vapes included through friends which may or may not involve payment as well as young people buying and selling them to one another.

“Older kids...sell vapes on the streets” (Group W).

These responses suggest that there are several methods for young people to obtain vapes, although access was primarily suggested to be from shops. This included illegal sales directly to a young person under the age of 18, or proxy sales that are not directly made to a young person, but an adult purchases the product on their behalf.

What do young people know about vapes and their impact?

A range of four vignettes presented as text messages were used to prompt discussion around knowledge of vapes and their impact. These were themed around the hidden use of vapes, the legal framework for vaping, addiction and the role of friendship groups. Young people across all groups lacked a comprehensive understanding of the legal framework around vape use. When the groups were presented with a vignette in the form of a mobile phone message which stated: “People in my school vape, is it illegal?” it prompted uncertainty and discussion.

“YP1: well, it’s not illegal to smoke it

YP2: It’s illegal to buy it” (Group X).

For some young people parental permission to vape was seen as important to ‘authorise’ vape use, for others school policy was key.

“YP1: It’s a rule you can’t but it isn’t illegal

YP2: If it is school policy you can’t have it” (Group W).

Many young people shared their knowledge of young people being able to buy vapes in local shops. There was a widespread awareness that young people should not be able to access them but a lack of clarity about the law prohibiting the *sale* rather than purchase of vapes by young people.

“Some shops need ID but others just allow you to buy vapes” (Group W).

“...They don’t have them on display, you have to give them ID and you have got to say to them I want a vape that is over 9000 puffs” (Group X).

“Once I was in [name of place] with my mate and she wanted one and she said I want a 6000 one and he said I can’t sell it to you...and he still sold it to her” (Group Y).

Consideration of issues such as sale by proxy were not raised by young people and they were also confused about whether they were able to vape legally once vapes had been obtained.

“I mean if it was illegal they wouldn’t serve them to young people at shops” (Group Z).

Levels of knowledge differed between groups, which may in part be attributable to age differences in participants. Older participants talked about unregulated vape products, recognising that there are legal limits described by approximate number of puffs in a product. They confirmed vapes exceeding the limits were nonetheless still available and purchased.

“There are actually some vapes that are illegal, and some shopkeepers still sell them like the 6000 puff ones” (Group Y).

Participants demonstrated differing levels of understanding of the potential harms of vape use. They raised the issue of a lack of knowledge in general about how harmful vapes are which fed into their lack of clarity about whether and in what ways vape use could cause harm. For example:

“That message has been out there for years and years, oh we don’t know this and we don’t know that. I feel like some people are going to be like how, how do you not know this” (Group X).

Young people within the groups did however frequently raise issues around potential lung damage as a harm of vaping and one group referenced the incidence of ‘popcorn lung’ but did not know what this was or how it was caused by vape use.

“So, weren’t they putting chemicals in vapes at one point that damaged your lungs and stuff?” (Group X).

“Bad for your lungs” (Group W).

This lack of clear messaging to young people about harms is problematic and creates confusion between vaping and the harms of tobacco smoking, where young people may incorrectly perceive vapes to be harm free or as harmful as tobacco. This issue is further complicated by a lack of knowledge about the levels of nicotine within vaping products and the use of unregulated vapes which may contain additional harmful content and unknown levels of nicotine.

Views differed on whether vaping was less harmful than tobacco smoking. Young people frequently moved between discussing vaping and discussing tobacco smoking. For some, vaping was perceived as better than smoking and a form of harm reduction.

“I feel like that’s why kids are leaning more towards the vaping side because they don’t want to smoke” (Group X).

For others, however, they felt there may be more control in smoking tobacco and quantifying how many cigarettes are smoked.

Young person 1: “I would just say it’s no different from smoking. It’s no different from smoking normally. If, anything it could become worse than smoking normally.

Young person 2: “Yeah, because there is more nicotine in a vape.”

Young person 1: “Exactly. You can control how many (cigarettes) you have in a daytime” (Group X).

This suggests a lack of clarity about the relative harms of smoking tobacco and vape use, but also a lack of knowledge about nicotine content within vaping products. Participants showed awareness of the presence of nicotine in vaping products. Across all groups it was noted that there can be a shift from social vaping to more continuous use and that vaping can be addictive.

“People are genuinely getting snappy because they are not getting their vape” (Group X).

“They are addicted to it, so they want to do it inside or outside” (Group W).

“They just keep doing it and doing it, it’s like oxygen or something isn’t it?” (Group Z).

It was unclear however whether participants understood the levels of nicotine content within vape products. One participant explained that they believed that YP do not understand the nicotine content.

“No, I don’t think it’s quite clear...I know some people that are literally buying the disposable ones, and they will go through a full disposable in a day, or two days and they don’t understand the nicotine content is so high...It’s causing unnecessary nicotine addiction. You don’t even have the option to get ones that don’t have nicotine in” (Group X).

There was some awareness that vapes with higher numbers of puffs may be unregulated but a corresponding sense that unregulated vapes may contain other unknown content, which could be harmful, as well as a stronger nicotine content, was absent from all groups. A lack of understanding of key differences between regulated and unregulated vapes is important to prevent further unknown health harms, particularly as participants discussed the ease with which unregulated vapes can be accessed by young people.

Environmental concerns about disposable vapes was not a strong theme within the group discussions. When prompted, one group mentioned the volume of litter.

Researcher: “Do you notice any rubbish from vapes anywhere?”

Young person: “There are batteries everywhere...they just throw it wherever they want” (Group Y).

What strategies do young people think would be most effective in supporting young people to understand the impact of the use of vapes?

Young people used their knowledge of smoking cessation support to suggest the potential for similar products to support cessation of vaping products. This included providing alternative vapes without nicotine and access to stop vaping support.

There were also suggestions for increased regulation, including placing vaping products out of view, like tobacco products, reducing promotion and making vaping products less appealing to young people through the removal of colours and flavours.

“Stop shops from advertising what vapes they have got” (Group X).

“So, the first thing I notice when I walk in a shop...the first thing I set my eyes on is the vapes” (Group X).

“Now they have shutters on tobacco and cigarettes right, why not vapes”(Group X).

One young person also raised concerns that too much regulation may lead to the use of unregulated products, as well as cigarettes.

Participants had a variety of views on how useful they believed health messages on potential harms would be in reducing vape use. There was also recognition that communicating health harms alone may not always be effective.

“I feel like even if you tell them [about the health risks] they will be like well yeah I don’t care, and they will still do it, but some will listen in the end” (Group Z).

Overall, participants did however still indicate the importance of clarifying the health impacts including on mental well-being.

“It’s bad for your health” (Group W).

“Addiction is bad for your mind” (Group W).

They also made suggestions for local promotion of health information about vapes.

Young person one: “Scrolling screen posters on bus stops...maybe handing out flyers and stuff”.

Young person two: “Posters definitely” (Group X).

One young person wondered whether an emphasis on the financial costs of vaping would also be important to young people.

“Would you rather spend over £500 a year on something you like to do or enjoy an addiction?” (Group X).

Many participants suggested increased support delivered within schools by specialist staff. Specialist staff were preferred to teachers, as they felt an in-depth understanding was necessary to address questions as they occur as inaccurate or delayed information could deter young people from seeking support.

“Going in to schools so rather than saying to teachers we need you to say this to them. I don’t think teachers” (Group X).

Young people discussed the role of peers in sharing information about vapes and given reflections on the influence of local role models shared during some of the activities it may be useful to consider the role of peers and older young people in sharing information about vapes and routes for support.

Strengths and limitations

The study is limited by the modest number of participants. The use of focus group discussion can limit involvement by some members of the group who may be less likely to speak in a group setting but a range of methods were used to gather feedback including written sticky notes alongside verbal contributions, support from youth workers known to the young people and the use of a comfortable familiar environment. The study is strengthened by a focus on discussions with young people from a range of backgrounds, ages and circumstances.

Key insights and recommendations

Findings suggest several implications which will have relevance both to and beyond Doncaster. The forthcoming ban on disposable vapes (HM Government 2024) alongside other measures to reduce access to vapes, such as the Tobacco and Vapes Bill (2023-24), provide an important context for further local action.

Recommendation one: There is an important need to tailor information and support to the varying patterns of vape use by young people. Targeted support to young people from groups with higher prevalence of vape use and those facing health inequalities is essential.

Young people who participated in this study suggest that vaping is widespread, particularly among secondary school young people, indicating a need for urgent attention to prevent widening health inequalities. Vaping was suggested to be influenced by a combination of factors such as peer social groups, local promotion, and the accessibility of appealing products.

Extant studies highlighted experimental use of vapes on social occasions although these were undertaken in 2015 and 2017 and may no longer reflect current trends (Moore et al. 2015, Bauld et al. 2017). More recently, Pinho-Gomes et al. (2023) conducted a survey with participants aged between 15 and 30 years and identified that about one in five participants currently used vapes at least monthly, with 1 in 10 using them daily. Discussions with the groups in this study instead emphasised more ubiquitous and regular vaping by young people, suggesting possible differences in patterns of use by specific groups and the potential for widening health inequalities. More everyday regular use has the potential for greater harms, including the development of nicotine addiction (Notley et al. 2020). Using unregulated products that may have a higher capacity creates further opportunity for nicotine addiction,

alongside the intake of additional harmful chemicals. Participants indicated that vaping was prevalent amongst young people of all genders but with some suggestions that females may vape more than males. This aligns with growing research identifying increased use amongst females (NHS 2021, ASH 2023).

Recommendation two: The provision of appropriate, accessible and reliable sources of information and support is key. Information and support designed with young people is likely to be beneficial in ensuring that it means their needs and requirements effectively.

Young people displayed both a lack of specific knowledge about vaping in relation to their health and the legal framework and also emphasised a need for the provision of appropriate information and support. The provision of appropriate, accessible and reliable sources of information and support is a key element, particularly where vaping is more prevalent and regularly undertaken. Information and support designed with young people is likely to be beneficial in ensuring that it means their needs and requirements effectively.

Recommendation three: Interventions which can harness the role of local older young people as role models in providing evidence-based peer information and support could be beneficial.

Narratives about peer pressure suggested a more complex relationship with vaping in social interactions as identified in prior research (Lucherini et al 2019). Young people did not necessarily feel overt pressure to vape, but rather a desire to align with their social group and older peers. Given the social nature of vaping and the known impact of peers on its uptake, interventions which can harness the role of local older young people as role models in providing evidence-based peer information and support could be beneficial (Asdigan et al. 2023).

Recommendation four: Utilising opportunities for health education on potential vaping harms through trained outreach and engagement staff would broaden access to information.

Young people described vaping a variety of settings including public spaces such as local parks and outside shops. This could present opportunities for health education on potential vaping harms through for example trained outreach and engagement staff to share information and discuss health harms of vaping, particularly for those who have never smoked tobacco products. Utilising a range of locations outside as well as inside schools would broaden the reach and accessibility of information. The hidden nature of vaping by some young people, may also indicate a need to educate families on identifying and addressing vaping by their young people, and provide them with accessible, relevant information to share and advice on approaches to use.

Recommendation five: There are important implications for local authorities in relation to their approaches to the commercial determinants of health and management of illegal trading.

Young people highlighted the role of colours and flavours in making vape products attractive, which supports the findings of several existing studies (Hilton et al 2016, Measham et al. 2016, Notley et al. 2022). Participants suggested the removal of colours and flavours may be an effective strategy to reduce appeal to young people and limit usage. The findings from this study identified very local routes for young people to obtain vapes, which meant that they were relatively easy to access. While increased regulation through the removal of vape products from view, plain packaging and removal or reduction of colours and flavours require national government regulation, there are important implications for local authorities in relation to their approaches to the commercial determinants of health and management of illegal trading.

Recommendation Six: Information and support which outlines the harms of tobacco and vape products are required, alongside a range of other interventions.

The findings here indicate that highlighting health concerns is important although it may not be sufficient alone. Pinho-Gomes et al. suggested that perceiving vapes as harmful might reduce their use, and also noted that many users seemed unaware of their potential harms

(Pinho-Gomes et al. 2023). In this study there were also low levels of understanding of health harms, and this was increased during discussions about the different harms between regulated and unregulated products. Information and support which outlines the harms of both types of products are therefore required, alongside a range of other interventions (Public Health England 2015).

Participants indicated an interest in services which can provide support akin to smoking cessation services. The type and availability of this support to young people requires careful consideration. Sanchez et al. noted that although there are similarities, there are also important differences between vapes and tobacco products that need to be considered in planning cessation services including factors such as the role of flavours, convenience and lack of self-awareness of vaping behaviours, a lack of trusted information and perceived social acceptability (Sanchez et al. 2021). This is supported by studies that also found an appetite from young people to stop vape use and a need to provide a variety of strategies and interventions that can engage young people with varying needs (Pbert et al. 2024, Amato et al. 2021).

Reflections on the co-creation process

At the end of the project, a facilitated workshop was organised to reflect on the co-created process of the study between the ERs and PH practitioners. A number of areas were explored including our initial expectations, key learning points and our plans for sharing and implementation of the findings. Figure four below shows the reflections gathered at the workshop.

Figure four: photograph of reflections

Reflections on the start of the study

Expectations of the project included the opportunity to build relationships as a team, an opportunity to undertake further learning alongside the need for good quality local insight about youth vaping which could inform local practice, and a commitment to involve young people in the study.

The team felt that ensuring the study was co-created from the outset was an important part of the process, particularly taking time to collectively think about and reflect on existing literature and local knowledge sources to inform the research questions so that there was a clear shared focus for the study.

Reflections on conducting the study

Being involved in the production of the project proposal, project materials such as participant information sheets and consent forms, and the ethics application led to a greater understanding of academic research processes and their purpose. The lack of a pressured timeframe in which to complete the research (beyond the teams' own timescales) meant that involvement in the study took place provided space and time to 'learn by doing' in a way that was practically focused but also had opportunities for skills workshops to be built into the process such as the thematic analysis workshops and time to reflect. The provision of training and support to engage in the research were therefore key elements.

There were shared values cross the team about the importance of young people's involvement in shaping the research as well as hearing and learning from young people's views and experiences through the data collection. The shared values meant that there was a real commitment to ensuring this was facilitated and actioned throughout the study.

For researchers, the specialist practical experience and in-depth local knowledge brought by public health practitioners within the team was critical in ensuring that the study was designed to meet local need, and any findings or recommendations would have the potential to be able to be implemented. Furthermore, the local connections of public health practitioners facilitated effective recruitment of potential research participants and in particular young people who may experience health inequalities. In addition, team members who were new to research were organised to work with more experienced team members both for focus group attendance and analysis tasks. Drawing on the different skills sets, and knowledge of team members was therefore an important part of the study and sat alongside a general openness to new ideas and approaches brought by different team members.

Project communication and co-ordination were seen as key elements of the study including a lead co-ordinator to organise the different elements of the project and opportunities for regular meetings and updates on progress to ensure all team members were included and informed as the study developed and responded to shifting circumstances.

In addition to the creation of knowledge about young people's views and experiences of youth vaping in their community, the team identified a range of learning specifically from the co-creation research process. The value of the multi-disciplinary team was seen as a key learning outcome alongside recognition of the value of embedded research in the local authority. The use of academic research processes also gave increased confidence in the findings.

Conducting research with young people provided multiple learning opportunities for the team. This included the value of conducting initial PPIE work with young people to support

the design of the study as well as an appreciation of the challenges and complexities of involving young people in qualitative research. There was key learning about the need to recognise the importance of ensuring sessions were not too long or had too many activities as engagement waned toward the end of the groups. Time to visit groups, to introduce ourselves, and build rapport alongside conducting research in environments that were familiar and comfortable to participants, were also important to create a more informal and relaxed atmosphere for data collection.

There were also differences between groups such as ages of participants and a need to adapt activities to the needs of different groups was also essential. This included providing the option of translated information for families and a video version of the participant information sheet.

Reflections on the end of the study

Overall, the team reflected an increased appreciation of the research process, and the different stages involved in planning and delivering a research project including co-creation, research ethics, data protection, recruiting and organising focus group sessions, data analysis and the development of recommendations for practice. Public health practitioners also cited developing new useful research skills such as thematic analysis and designing activities by and for young people. As a new entity within the local authority and nationally, a deeper understanding of the role and purpose of the HDRC was developed within the team alongside important learning for the embedded researchers about how the HDRC can work in practice with local authority colleagues.

There were suggestions for areas of future improvement including:

- the provision of more training sessions around different aspects of research
- practical suggestions to improve recording of focus groups,
- adjusting adult expectations of young people's engagement with all activities in the sessions.

Overall, positive reflections were shared across the team about the study including feeling more confident and informed, looking forward to sharing the findings and being hopeful for implementing recommendations.

Impact

The findings suggest the need for a coordinated response to the issue of young people using vapes at both local and national levels. By listening to local young people, practitioners felt more confident to take a local approach to responding to this public health issue. In Doncaster a specific Task & Finish Group, bringing together a range of stakeholders from across the local authority, has been established to consider and prepare for the implications of the upcoming Tobacco and Vaping Bill implementation using the findings of this study. A suite of resources including infographics and session plans, for educators, youth workers, families and young people are in development for use locally. Commissioners and service providers of tobacco control and young people's services are reviewing current smoking and vaping cessation offers and there may be an implication to review service specifications and/or commission further support services.

Dissemination

The team are identifying a wide range of opportunities to share both the findings of the research as well as the learning from collaborative working between embedded researchers and local authority public health practitioners. This includes an article in the 'Perspectives in Public Health' journal (Dowrick et al. 2025). We are also identifying opportunities to share the findings and learning through opportunities to present at academic conferences, public dissemination events, and sharing through established networks interested in tobacco and vaping such as the South Yorkshire Regional Tobacco Control Alliance and the Yorkshire and Humber Community of Improvers.

Groups of young people that took part in the study were asked if they would be interested in developing some of the materials and resources and this will be included in the development process.

Next steps

It is intended that continued engagement with local young people will support the building of a legacy of young person's involvement in local research and the development of local public health strategies and solutions, particularly with groups who experience greater health inequalities. Carrying out this research, has highlighted further opportunities for research to explore young people's views and responses to the upcoming Tobacco and Vapes Bill and additional funding to support the development of this work is being sought.

Conclusion

This study supports existing findings about the appeal of vaping products to young people. The findings also add important knowledge about experiences of young people from a range of backgrounds where vaping has been identified as more prevalent locally and which mirrors local health inequality data. There was a lack of awareness of legal frameworks and health harms of vaping products amongst young people in the study. Young people's suggestions on support to reduce vaping point towards several policy and practice interventions for use in local authority settings, including providing accurate and clear information on vape harms, enhancing support services, and reducing vape access and appeal.

As a co-created study involving public health practitioners and embedded researchers within a newly created Health Determinants Research Collaboration (HDRC) the study also points to

a range of benefits of collaborative research undertaken in a local authority setting in increasing research capacity and sharing knowledge in a multi-disciplinary team.

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